

WHAT IS REINCARNATE

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry by maximising the life cycle of buildings, construction products, and materials. The project targets a reduction of construction and demolition waste (CDW) by 80%, an increase in reusability of building components, and a reduction of sector emissions by 70%.

Within this context, early-stage detection of degradation in building materials—such as crack formation in masonry—is essential to enable timely maintenance, prevent structural deterioration, and support reuse-oriented decision-making. These objectives are supported by digital technologies such as artificial intelligence and data-driven assessment methods.

Figure 1. An overview of a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture and the training process

CONTEXT AND INNOVATION

The assessment of structural condition in masonry buildings remains a key challenge for enabling circular construction practices, particularly when damage develops progressively and is not easily detectable at early stages. Crack formation is one of the most common indicators of structural degradation in masonry, and its timely detection is essential to prevent further deterioration and support maintenance and reuse decisions. Conventional inspection approaches rely heavily on manual visual assessment, which is often subjective, time-consuming, and difficult to scale across large building stocks.

This work addresses these limitations through the development of an AI-based, non-destructive methodology for crack detection and assessment using image data. The approach combines machine learning models, such as Random Forest and XGBoost, with deep learning architectures including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and UNet, enabling both classification and pixel-level segmentation of cracks. A custom dataset of masonry surfaces is collected and annotated to support supervised training and evaluation.

Aligned with the REINCARNATE innovation “Building Inspection & Valuation” and the WP1-related tool “Predictive Life-Cycle Information”, the approach improves reliability, scalability, and objectivity of inspections and supports lifecycle-oriented decision-making.

DEMONSTRATION AND RESULTS

A custom dataset of masonry images was collected using controlled acquisition conditions. Images were annotated with binary crack masks using LabelMe, enabling supervised training.

Machine learning models (Random Forest, XGBoost) were trained on handcrafted features, while deep learning models (CNN, UNet) were trained directly on images. CNN achieved up to 89% accuracy. UNet achieved IoU up to 0.81 and Dice coefficient up to 0.89.

These results demonstrate reliable detection and segmentation of cracks, including fine patterns not easily captured manually.

Figure 2. Proposed Crack Detection Framework

TECHNICAL HIGHLIGHTS

- AI-based crack detection using computer vision
- ML (Random Forest, XGBoost) and DL (CNN, UNet)
- Annotated dataset using LabelMe
- Feature-based and end-to-end learning
- High-precision crack segmentation

IMPACTS AND REPLICATION

CATEGORY	FOCUS	CONTRIBUTION LEVEL
Scientific	Integration of ML and DL for crack detection	High
Societal	Supports safer infrastructure via early detection	Medium
Techno-economic	Enables automated inspection workflows	Medium

REPLICATION POTENTIAL

Applicable to masonry structures with available image data. Requires annotated datasets and suitable acquisition conditions. Transferable to other defects with adapted training data.

Original Image

Grayscale Image

Predicted: CRACKED

LINKS

<https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/>

CONTACTS

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